

Expert Judgment Template Learning Outcomes

Instructions

You have been selected to evaluate a series of indicators that will allow us to assess the learning outcome _____.

The evaluation of this set of indicators is of great relevance, as it will allow us to identify how accurate these indicators are in assessing the learning outcome of _____. In this way, your collaboration will contribute to improving the self-assessment and quality management process in the institution. We appreciate your valuable collaboration.

Judge's Information

- **Full Name:**
- **Academic Background:**
- **Areas of Professional Experience:**
- **Years of Experience:**
- **Current Position:**
- **Institution:**

Objective of the Expert Judgment

Conduct a content validation of the proposed indicators for evaluating the indicators of the learning outcome_____.

Indicators for Evaluation

Each subset of indicators is associated with a learning outcome, and you will help us by providing your rating as an expert in teaching and topics related to the learning outcome.

Below, we present a description of each rating you can give along with an explanation of the criteria you will use to evaluate the indicators.

When evaluating each indicator, you should assign a score between 1 and 4 (as indicated in the following table) based on your criteria for clarity, coherence, and relevance of each individual indicator. You will also assign a score between 1 and 4 for all indicators related to the objective in question in the Sufficiency category.

TEGORY	RATING	INDICATOR
SUFFICIENCY The indicators are sufficient to obtain the measurement of the learning outcome according to the agency's	1. Does not meet the criteria	The indicators are not sufficient to measure the dimension.
	2. Low Level	The indicators measure some aspect of the dimension but do not

definition.		correspond to the entire dimension.
	3. Moderate Level	Other indicators need to be incorporated to fully assess the learning outcome.
	4. High Level	The indicators are sufficient.
CLARITY The indicator is easily understood, i.e., its syntax is appropriate.	1. Does not meet the criteria.	The indicator is not clear.
	2. Low Level	The indicator requires significant modifications in the use of words or their arrangement.
	3. Moderate Level	A specific modification of some terms of the indicator is required.
	4. High Level	The indicator is clear, with appropriate semantics and syntax.
COHERENCE The indicator has a logical relationship with the learning outcome being measured.	1. Does not meet the criteria.	The item has no logical relationship with the dimension.
	2. Low Level	The indicator has a tangential relationship with the dimension.
	3. Moderate Level	The indicator has a moderate relationship with the dimension being measured.
	4. High Level	The indicator is completely related to the dimension being measured.
RELEVANCE The indicator is essential or important, i.e., it must be included.	1. Does not meet the criteria	The indicator can be eliminated without affecting the measurement of the dimension.
	2. Low Level	The indicator has some relevance, but another indicator may include what this one measures.
	3. Moderate Level	The indicator is relatively important.
	4. High Level	The indicator is very relevant and must be included.

*The syntactic structure refers to the order of words, parts of sentences, sentences, and phrases, to express ideas logically and appropriately, i.e., without ambiguities or unintelligibly.

Tables for Recording Evaluations

In the following tables, a subset of indicators associated with an learning outcome will be presented. You are expected to assign a rating for the categories of coherence, relevance, and clarity, and a general score (where you give a single score to all items) in the sufficiency category for each learning outcome.

When reviewing the indicators, consider the following: The indicators are directly derived from the definition of the learning outcome. The definition is found in the header of each table. They must be observable and evaluable. They must be feasible and achievable by students at the end of the learning period in their training. They will be evaluated in an integrated manner, i.e., they will be applied together to assess the learning outcome in its entirety. These courses will be evaluated both in service courses and in courses specific to the curriculum of each of the careers participating in the accreditation processes. The evaluation focuses on the students' ability to demonstrate the achievement of these indicators through learning activities.

Learning outcome					
Definition:					
Indicators/items	Sufficiency	Coherence	Relevance	Clarity	Comments

This template was adapted from:

Aguilar-Cordero, J. F. (2023). Exploración de la percepción estudiantil sobre la implementación guiones para promover la regulación socialmente compartida del aprendizaje. *Revista Electrónica Calidad en la Educación Superior*, 14(2), 364-390

Escobar-Pérez, J., & Cuervo-Martínez, Á. (2008). Validez de contenido y juicio de expertos: Una aproximación a su utilización. *Avances En Medición*, 6(2), 42–53. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.32870/ap.v9n2.993>